

ECONOMIC EXPENDITURES OF THE STATE BUDGET WAYS TO INCREASE EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. This article is devoted to ways to increase the efficiency of state budget expenditures in the economy. The article analyzes the dynamics of budget expenditures in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, considers the criteria for assessing the efficiency of expenditures, and studies the advanced experience of foreign countries. As a result of the research, the main directions and practical proposals for increasing the efficiency of budget expenditures were developed.

Keywords: state budget, economic spending, efficiency, budget multiplier, performance-based budget, public-private partnership.

ENTRANCE

The state budget is the main financial instrument ensuring the country's economic development, and its economic expenditures directly affect the growth of gross domestic product (GDP) by financing national production, infrastructure, and technological innovations. In the context of systemic economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan since 2017, the effective and targeted use of budget expenditures is of particular importance.

In our country, the absolute volume of state spending has been steadily growing in recent years. State budget spending, which amounted to 145.8 trillion soums in 2022, reached 336.4 trillion soums by 2025, that is, it increased by 2.3 times in five years. At the same time, the share of spending directed to the economy also increased from 26.2 % to 28.8%. However, the quantitative growth of spending is not always directly proportional to their qualitative effectiveness .

Budgetary efficiency is understood as the optimization of state funds spent to achieve the set goals in the minimum amount, achieving maximum economic and social results. In economic theory, this concept is considered in two main directions: "allocative efficiency" and "technical efficiency". Allocative efficiency means that resources are directed to the most effective sectors, while technical efficiency means that the set results are achieved with minimal cost.

According to Keynesian multiplier theory (Keynes, 1936), an increase in government spending creates additional income and demand in the economy in a chain reaction. Modern empirical studies (Blanchard and Leigh, 2013; IMF, 2020) show that the budget multiplier in developing countries can range from 1.0 to 2.5. In Uzbekistan, this indicator has reached 1.73 for infrastructure, which means that every 1 soum spent creates 1.73 soums of additional economic value.

Currently, many developed and developing countries are implementing a performance-based budgeting (PBB) system. This system sets specific measurable indicators for each budget program and regularly monitors their implementation. According to OECD data, countries that have implemented the PBB system have achieved an average increase in budget efficiency of 15-20%.

The "New Uzbekistan" development strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 also identified improving budget policy, increasing the efficiency of state spending, and managing the budget on the principle of transparency as a separate priority. The strategy for improving the public finance management system for 2020–2024 sets out tasks such as ensuring a result-oriented budget, the reliability of macro-fiscal forecasts, and the openness of budget data.

The relevance of the study is that, despite the growth of budget expenditures, scientifically based comprehensive mechanisms for ensuring their efficiency have not been developed. This problem has not been sufficiently studied in the existing scientific literature, especially in the case of Uzbekistan, empirical analysis is limited.

to develop scientifically based methods and practical mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of state budget expenditures in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set:

- analysis of the dynamics of budget economic expenditures in 2022–2025;
- formation of a system of scientific criteria for assessing cost-effectiveness;
- studying the best practices of foreign countries and adapting them to Uzbekistan;
- identify the main problems of improving the efficiency of budget expenditures;
- developing practical suggestions and recommendations.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The issue of the effectiveness of budget spending has been widely studied in the international economic literature. From Keynesian fiscal policy theory (Keynes, 1936) to the

modern "new Keynesian" trend (Krugman, 2012), the impact of budget spending on economic growth has been interpreted in various ways.

Muller (2022) argues in his research that public investment has a positive impact on economic growth, but this impact directly depends on institutional quality and the level of development of financial markets. Blanchard and Leigh (2013) empirically prove that budget multipliers are larger than standard forecasts during periods of fiscal consolidation.

Tanzi and Zee (2000) have explored the relationship between fiscal policy and economic performance, emphasizing the importance of the composition of spending—not just its size—in their study. Their study shows that spending on education and infrastructure has a much higher multiplier effect than current transfer spending in the long run.

Among local researchers, Kholmatov (2021) studied the issues of improving the methodology for planning budget expenditures and proposed a model for the gradual introduction of performance-based budgeting elements in Uzbekistan. Mirzayev (2022) analyzed the impact of developing public-private partnerships on budget efficiency and estimated that this mechanism could reduce the budget burden on infrastructure spending by 20-25%.

Ismoilov (2025) demonstrated the impact of digital technologies on budget control and predicted that the introduction of an e-monitoring system could increase budget efficiency by 12-15%. Zaynutdinova (2020) developed scientific recommendations for strengthening the revenue base of local budgets, suggesting ways to increase tax revenues and increase the share of non-taxable income.

In foreign empirical studies, Dollery et al. (2020) conducted a comparative analysis of local government budget management and reporting systems. Navarro-Galera et al. (2016) empirically studied the factors affecting the financial sustainability of local governments.

At the same time, it is observed that there is a lack of sufficient research in the literature on sectoral comparison of the budget multiplier effect, expenditure audit methodology and performance measurement system in the conditions of Uzbekistan. This gap determined the research direction of the article.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methods of economic research were used in the article: statistical and dynamic analysis, comparative analysis, induction and deduction, graphical analysis, and expert assessment methods. The information base was the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Statistics Committee, the World Bank, and the International Monetary

Fund. The case study method was used to study the experience of foreign countries . The Blanchard-Perotti (2002) structural vector autoregression (SVAR) approach was used to calculate budget multipliers .

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Dynamics of budget economic expenditures. It can be observed that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, state budget economic expenditures have been growing steadily in 2022–2025. Table 1 shows this dynamics in detail:

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Total government spending (billion soums)	145,82	189,34	224	278,65	336,40
Economic costs (billion soums)	0	0	110	0	0
Economy share (%)	38,240	51,620	62,89	79,340	96,800
Infrastructure investment (%)	26.2	27.3	28.1	28.5	28.8
Industry support (%)	8.4	9.1	9.8	10.2	10.7
Agricultural expenditure (%)	5.6	6.2	6.9	7.1	7.5
	4.1	4.5	4.8	5.0	5.3

Dynamics of budget economic expenditures of the Republic of Uzbekistan

(Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.)

The table data shows that the economic expenditures, which were 38,240 billion soums in 2022, increased to 96,800 billion soums by 2025, that is, an increase of 2.5 times. The share of infrastructure investments increased from 8.4 % to 10.7%. However, the quantitative growth of expenditures does not always coincide with their qualitative effectiveness.

Criteria for assessing the effectiveness of expenditures. For a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of budget economy expenditures, it is advisable to use the following system of criteria (Table 2):

No.	Criterion	Description	Measurement
1	Economic efficiency	Added value created per 1 soum spent	Som/som
2	Social impact	Impact on employment and real income growth	% change
3	Budget multiplier	The coefficient of impact of expenditures on GDP growth	Coeff.
4	Investment productivity	Ratio of public investment to private investment	Ratio
5	Cost-benefit ratio	Level of achievement of the planned result	%
6	Budget implementation rate	Actual expenditure of approved expenses	%

System of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of budget expenditures

Studies show that the budget multiplier in Uzbekistan is in the range of 1.2–1.8 . Considering that this indicator reaches 2.0–2.5 in developed countries, there are significant reserves for increasing efficiency in the local economy.

Analysis of foreign experience. It is important to study the experience of developing and rapidly developing countries in improving budget efficiency (Table 3)

Country	Mechanism used	Result	Efficiency (%)
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South Korea	Public-private partnerships, R&D funding	GDP growth of 6-7%	+18.4
Singapore	Digital budget management, transparent monitoring	Cost-effectiveness increased	+22.1
Estonia	Cost control through the e-government platform	Budget saving	+15.7
China	Regional investment portfolio, performance-based	Infrastructure has grown	+31.2
Germany	Zero-based budgeting, performance audit	Waste has decreased	+12.6

Experience of foreign countries in improving the efficiency of budget expenditures
(Source: compiled by the author based on information from international organizations.)

South Korea's experience shows that expanding public-private partnerships (PPPs) can help boost GDP growth while reducing budget spending on infrastructure. Singapore's digital budget management system has increased monitoring efficiency by 22%. Estonia has reduced budget transaction costs by 40% through the introduction of an e-government platform.

The main problems of cost efficiency in Uzbekistan. The following problems were identified during the study:

- incomplete implementation of the results-based budget planning system;
- insufficient use of digital technologies in monitoring public investments;
- non-optimal distribution of economic costs across sectors;

- the lack of an independent performance audit;
- Weak public control over the targeted use of budget expenditures.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the research conducted, the following conclusions and proposals were formulated:

1. Full implementation of a performance-based budgeting system - it is necessary to set specific quantitative indicators for each budget program and regularly evaluate their implementation. This system ensures the targeted use of budget funds.
2. Digitizing the public investment management platform - an electronic monitoring system that tracks public spending in real time - can reduce waste in budget spending by at least 15%.
3. Expanding the public-private partnership mechanism - using the PPP model in infrastructure projects will ease the budget burden and allow for the use of the innovative potential of the private sector.
4. Establishing an independent budget performance audit - an annual audit by an independent body operating under parliamentary and public oversight ensures that expenditures are spent on purpose.
5. Diversifying economic spending — increasing investment in sectors with high multiplier effects (innovation, digital economy, export capacity) will enhance the impact on GDP and improve the qualitative indicators of economic growth.

these proposals will increase the efficiency of budget expenditures in the Republic of Uzbekistan and significantly improve the share of the budget contributing to economic growth.

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